

Personality Type and Motivational Factors Affecting Career Shift among Licensed Professional Teachers

Marie Shiel Idanan Pascual

BCI Central Philippines

Research Department, Makati City, Philippines

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759480>

Published Date: 07-August-2025

Abstract: This article aimed to explore the personality types and motivational factors that influence Licensed Professional Teachers (LPTs) to shift into non-teaching roles. A total of ten (10) LPTs participated in the study, with nine (9) employed in the private sector and one (1) from the public sector. Qualitative research was employed, specifically utilizing the case study method. Data were analyzed using frequency, percentage, and thematic analysis techniques. Most participants were female, aged between 26 and 27, and held bachelor's degrees. They typically held full-time administrative roles in the private sector, earning monthly salaries ranging from 15,000 to 30,000 pesos. The most prevalent personality types identified were ISTJ (Introverted, Sensing, Thinking, Judging) and ESTJ (Extraverted, Sensing, Thinking, Judging)—both of which are associated with being logical, detail-oriented, and dependable. Additionally, key extrinsic motivations for shifting careers included the DepEd recruitment process, competitive compensation, and better work-life balance. Intrinsic motivation was largely driven by the pursuit of personal fulfillment. The study's findings highlight the importance of individualized career pathing programs for freshmen teacher education students, particularly those who are evaluating their future choices. Meanwhile, in response to increased career shifting among Licensed Professional Teachers (LPTs), it suggests offering MBTI assessments alongside entrance and qualifying tests at the start of the academic year, followed by workshops and seminars at the end of the first year. These findings can help the Office of Student Affairs (OSA) and other stakeholders develop responsive, personality-based support services. The researcher recommends that flexible workshops and counseling should also be offered to help teacher education students match their strengths with their career ambitions. Finally, collaboration among administrators, faculty, psychologists, and guidance counselors is critical for increasing teacher education students' commitment to the teaching profession and promoting long-term growth.

Keywords: personality type, motivational factors, career shift, Licensed Professional Teachers, non-teaching roles, MBTI, career pathing program.

I. INTRODUCTION

Teaching is a dynamic and rewarding profession that is much more than information transmission. One has to possess the skills in planning, instruction, classroom management, and evaluation to foster a positive learning environment.

Even before K-12 was introduced, middle-class Filipinos already preferred teaching as a career because of the monetary encouragement in the form of scholarships and student aid programs. However, this does not apply to those graduates who do not pursue teaching; they are mostly individuals who took admission into State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) just for availing free education (Panlaqui and Bardemorilla, 2023).

It is thus not surprising that education graduates often report facing diverse global and local challenges, including career shifting. These are licensed teachers who for various reasons do not apply their teaching profession; most of them abandon the teaching profession and take non-teaching careers.

Career shifting is one of the most discussed topics, not just in our country but globally. As explained by Rice; Akkermans & Kubasch; and Kober et al. (as cited in Nalis, Kubicek, and Korunka, 2021), career shifting has become more prevalent across the globe. A career shift is defined as a move from one occupation or field to another with significant differences in responsibilities or skills or area of work. The reason for this could be many such as change in interests, type of personality, motivation, desire for personal development, or even advancement in career opportunities.

Personality is important in selecting teaching as a career. It affects the job satisfaction of an individual by influencing how he or she perceives the work environment, students, and colleagues, as well as the demands of the job. In relation to this, motivation is critical in the choice of teaching as a profession. It drives why one chooses this profession, what expectations one has from this career, and commitment to the role.

Teachers are greatly responsible for the development of students, intellectually, socially, and emotionally; therefore, they are important in personal achievement as well as societal advancement. They are the most essential human resource in keeping the life of educational services (Yurt, 2022). They forge strong targeted relationships with students, administrators, and parents to support continuous education and development. According to Hunzicker (as cited in Glass, 2022), professional teachers have credentials that include degrees and licensure advanced certification.

However, some Filipino teachers opt not to continue in the education field after college, instead choosing careers in other industries (Abulon et al., n.d.). Several factors contribute to these challenges; beyond differences in personality and motivation, one major issue is the prolonged recruitment process at the Department of Education (DepEd). To become a Licensed Professional Teacher (LPT), candidates must first complete a four-year education degree from an accredited university. Afterwards, they are required to successfully complete the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) conducted by the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC). However, despite their education, qualifications, licenses, and credentials, applicants face a lengthy hiring process at DepEd due to the large number of candidates. Even after the Registry of Qualified Applicants (RQA) is published, being listed does not guarantee immediate employment; placement depends on available vacancies caused by retirements, resignations, or other factors.

Conversely, Panlaqui and Bardemorilla (2023) discovered in their study that graduates pursue non-teaching careers because of factors such as low commitment to the teaching profession, external influences, more competitive salaries, opportunities to support their passions, prospects for growth, and the desire for flexibility and work-life balance. Additionally, many are not dedicated to the profession because it was not their own choice, and they lack access to career guidance or counselling. In addition, educational institutions should encourage activities that strengthen education graduates' commitment to a teaching career. Moreover, this could involve offering thorough career guidance and counselling services to help graduates understand the significance and opportunities within the teaching profession (Laher, 2024).

Although numerous studies have explored the factors behind career shifts among professionals generally, there is limited research specifically focused on LPTs, especially regarding their personality types and motivational factors. Most existing research tends to emphasize aspects such as salary, workload, and job satisfaction, often overlooking how personality types as classified by the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) and intrinsic and extrinsic motivation affect LPTs' decisions to pursue non-teaching careers. This gap presents an opportunity to gain a deeper understanding of the personal and motivational factors influencing career shifts among LPTs, which could inform more tailored career pathing. Furthermore, the findings could help teacher education students and school administrators develop policies and practices aimed at reducing career shifts and improving overall job satisfaction.

Finally, the study also sought to identify which personality traits and motivational factors most significantly affect job satisfaction and why LPTs leave the profession. By revealing these factors, the researcher hopes to support LPTs, teacher education students, and school administrators in developing targeted programs—potentially integrated into curricula—to address career shifting and promote greater commitment to teaching.

Considering the context above, the researcher, an LPT, currently working in the construction and engineering industry, observed a growing trend of LPTs shifting to non-teaching roles in both public and private sectors. This inspired a deeper investigation into the rationale behind these career shifts. Motivated by this and aligned with the researcher's goal to become an instructor and psychologist specializing in career counselling, the study aimed to explore the personality types and motivational factors influencing LPTs to shift careers. The objective was to generate insights that could lead to practical solutions.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Design

This research adopted a qualitative research design, using the case study method. A case study represents a qualitative method that encompasses a thorough, contextual analysis of a single instance or a small number of instances within their authentic setting. This approach is especially useful when the distinctions between the phenomenon and its surroundings are not distinctly outlined. According to Yin (as cited in Balais, 2020), the primary purpose of this research design is explanatory—to clarify causal relationships in real-world situations that are too complex to be effectively studied using surveys or experimental methods. The case study method aims to thoroughly investigate complex issues and understand them from multiple perspectives. Additionally, it provides comprehensive insight into a specific issue, individual, classroom, policy, institution, program, or country, with the goal of generating knowledge and/or guiding policy formulation and professional practices (Balais, 2020). This research study was conceptualized to explore the personality types of LPTs, as well as their motivational factors for shifting careers, which may have influenced their shift to non-teaching roles. In this context, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How may the profile of the participants be described in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Civil Status
 - 1.3. Gender
 - 1.4. Highest Educational Attainment;
 - 1.5. Employment Status
 - 1.6. Nature of Work and/or Job Title
 - 1.7. Sector Employment Type
 - 1.8. Monthly Salary
2. What is the personality type of the participants as measured by the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI)?
3. What are the motivational factors of the participants to shift careers?
4. What implications could be drawn based on the findings of the study?

B. Participants

The study involved ten (10) LPTs as participants, with nine (9) from the private sector and one (1) from the public sector, selected through purposive sampling. These participants were chosen because the researcher believed they had firsthand experience teaching at private schools, had gone through the DepEd recruitment process, and were able to be included on the RQA list, which eventually led them to shift their careers to non-teaching roles, enabling them to provide accurate and well-founded responses.

TABLE 1. DISTRIBUTION OF PARTICPANTS

Sectors	N
LPT from Public Sector (non-teaching roles)	1
LPTs from Private Sector (non-teaching roles)	9
Total	10

C. Instrument

The study utilized survey questionnaires, adopted standardized personality tests, alongside researcher-designed interviews questions, all outlined for LPTs working in non-teaching roles. Part I gathered demographic information from the participants through survey questionnaires, including age, civil status, gender, highest level of education, employment status, nature of work and/or job title, type of employment sector, and monthly salary. Part II focused on various personality

dimensions adopted from the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI), originally developed by Isabel Briggs Myers and her mother, Katharine Cook Briggs, based on Carl Jung's theory of psychological types. This section included standardized personality tests designed to collect information on participants' perspectives and personalities, as well as how these factors influenced the career shifts of LPTs. Part III consisted of an interview guide aimed at collecting data about the participants' experiences, influences, and motivational factors related to the career shifts of LPTs.

The survey questionnaires were used to determine demographic information and data about the participants. The adopted standardized personality tests, specifically the MBTI, was used to identify personality types, as it was a widely recognized and validated tool. Meanwhile, the interview guide questions on motivational factors were researcher-developed, drawing from the researcher's own ideas and experiences. The suitability and alignment of these instruments with the study were reviewed and validated by the dean, panellists, thesis adviser, and the expert validators.

D. Data Analysis Plan

This study aimed to identify the participants' demographic profiles, personality types, and motivational factors that contributed to their career shift into non-teaching roles. Frequency and percentage distribution were employed to describe the participants' demographic profiles and to represent their personality types.

To analyse the interview data, thematic analysis was employed. This qualitative method assists in identifying, examining, and interpreting recurring patterns or themes within the data. It is frequently used in fields like psychology, sociology, and various social sciences to explore the meanings, experiences, and viewpoints shared by participants.

As noted by Laher (2024), Braun and Clarke outline six essential steps in thematic analysis: engaging deeply with the data, creating codes, constructing themes, reviewing those themes, defining and naming them, and composing the final report. This approach involves a comprehensive examination of the dataset to pinpoint significant patterns and themes. It is an introspective method where the researcher's individual viewpoints are vital for interpreting and analysing the data.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section of the study elaborates the results and translates the gathered data on the demographic profile, personality type and motivational factors identified by the Licensed Professional Teachers leading them to shift career in to non-teaching roles.

The demographic profile, personality type and motivational factors identified by the Licensed Professional Teachers are presented in table 2.

TABLE 2. DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE, PERSONALITY TYPE AND MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS OF THE PARTICIPANTS

Case No.	Code Name of LPT	Demographic Profile	Personality Type (MBTI)	Motivational Factors
1	"Love"	27-year-old, married with two children, female, college graduate, freelancer, administrative support, construction company, private sector, salary range between ₱31,000 - ₱60,000	Introverted, Sensing, Feeling, and Judging (ISFJ). ISFJs are loyal, dependable, hardworking caregivers who are deeply committed to their loved ones and traditions. They often operate behind the scenes, offering practical support and creating a stable, harmonious environment, and they notice the little things that make a big difference to others.	DepEd Recruitment Process, Competitive Salary, Personal Fulfillment, Work-life Balance, Lighter Workload, Work from Home, Stress-free
2	"Arki"	23-year-old, single, male, college graduate, full time, junior researcher, construction and engineering company, private sector,	Extraverted, Sensing, Thinking, and Judging (ESTJ). ESTJs are decisive, responsible, reliable, and goal-oriented leaders who excel at organizing people and tasks to achieve practical results. They value tradition,	DepEd Recruitment Process, Competitive Salary, Personal Fulfillment, Work-life Balance, Lighter Workload, Healthy Work

		salary range between ₱15,000 and ₱30,000	honesty, and efficiency, and can be very direct in their communication.	Environment, Work from Home, Stress-free
3	“Angel”	26-year-old, single, female, college graduate, full time, administrative support, contemporary Pentecostal church, private sector, monthly salary range between ₱15,000 and ₱30,000	Introverted, Sensing, Thinking, and Perceiving (ISTP). ISTPs are independent, curious, and resourceful problem-solvers who excel at understanding how things work and fixing them. They are often action-oriented and enjoy hands-on activities, new experiences, and the freedom to explore and improvise.	DepEd Recruitment Process, Competitive Salary, Personal Fulfillment, Work-life Balance, Lighter Workload, Healthy Work Environment, Stress-free
4	“Cupcake”	29-year-old, married with two (2) children, female, college graduate, freelancer, administrative support, direct employer, monthly salary range between ₱31,000 and ₱60,000	Introverted, Sensing, Thinking, and Judging (ISTJ). ISTJs are dependable, responsible, detail-oriented, and hardworking individuals who value tradition, order, and integrity. They excel at organizing and executing tasks methodically, ensuring that duties are fulfilled accurately and efficiently.	DepEd Recruitment Process, Competitive Salary, Personal Fulfillment, Work-life Balance, Healthy Work Environment, Work from Home
5	“Princess”	27-year-old, single, female, master’s unit earner, full time, research consultant, construction and engineering company, private sector, monthly salary range between ₱31,000 and ₱60,000	Introverted, Sensing, Thinking, and Judging (ISTJ). ISTJs are dependable, responsible, detail-oriented, and hardworking individuals who value tradition, order, and integrity. They excel at organizing and executing tasks methodically, ensuring that duties are fulfilled accurately and efficiently.	DepEd Recruitment Process, Competitive Salary, Personal Fulfillment, Work-life Balance, Lighter Workload, Healthy Work Environment, Work from Home, Career Development Opportunities, Stress-free
6	“Dimple”	26-year-old, single, female, college graduate, full time, operation expert, healthcare company, private sector, monthly salary range between ₱31,000 and ₱60,000	Extraverted, Sensing, Thinking, and Judging (ESTJ). ESTJs are decisive, responsible, reliable, and goal-oriented leaders who excel at organizing people and tasks to achieve practical results. They value tradition, honesty, and efficiency, and can be very direct in their communication.	DepEd Recruitment Process, Competitive Salary, Personal Fulfillment, Work-life Balance, Career Development Opportunities
7	“Queen”	28-year-old, single, female, college graduate, full time, youth development officer, municipality hall, public sector, monthly salary range between ₱15,000 and ₱30,000	Extraverted, Sensing, Thinking, and Judging (ESTJ). ESTJs are decisive, responsible, reliable, and goal-oriented leaders who excel at organizing people and tasks to achieve practical results. They value tradition, honesty, and efficiency, and can be very direct in their communication.	DepEd Recruitment Process, Competitive Salary, Personal Fulfillment, Healthy Work Environment, Career Development Opportunities
8	“Buttercup”	25-year-old, single, female, college graduate, full time, senior research consultant, construction and engineering company, private sector, monthly salary range between ₱31,000 and ₱60,000	Extraverted, Sensing, Feeling, Perceiving (ESFP). ESFPs are lively, spontaneous, and charming individuals who love to be at the center of attention and bring joy to others. They are practical, hands-on, and excel at living in the moment, often pursuing new and exciting experiences.	DepEd Recruitment Process, Competitive Salary, Personal Fulfillment, Work-life Balance, Lighter Workload, Healthy Work Environment, Work from Home

9	“Sweet”	27-year-old, single female, master’s unit earner freelance, social media manager, direct employer, monthly salary range between ₱15,000 and ₱30,000	Introverted, Sensing, Thinking, and Judging (ISTJ). ISTJs are dependable, responsible, detail-oriented, and hardworking individuals who value tradition, order, and integrity. They excel at organizing and executing tasks methodically, ensuring that duties are fulfilled accurately and efficiently.	DepEd Recruitment Process, Competitive Salary, Personal Fulfillment, Work-life Balance, Lighter Workload, Work from Home, Career Development Opportunities
10	“Phoenix”	26-year-old, single, male, college graduate, full time, food and beverage server, restaurant industry, private sector, monthly salary range between ₱15,000 and ₱30,000	Introverted, Sensing, Thinking, and Judging (ISTJ). ISTJs are dependable, responsible, detail-oriented, and hardworking individuals who value tradition, order, and integrity. They excel at organizing and executing tasks methodically, ensuring that duties are fulfilled accurately and efficiently.	DepEd Recruitment Process, Competitive Salary, Personal Fulfillment, Lighter Workload, Healthy Work Environment, Stress-free

A. Demographic Profile of the Participants

Age: The majority of the LPTs 8 (80%) were between the ages of 26 and 29, while the remaining 2 (20%) were 23 and 25 years old.

Gender: Among the LPTs who shifted to non-teaching roles, 8 (80%) were female, while 2 (20%) were male.

Civil Status: The majority of the LPTs were single, comprising 8 (80%) participants, while 2 (20%) participants were married with two children each.

Highest Educational Attainment: Most of the LPTs were college graduates, making up 8 (80%) participants, while the remaining 2 (20%) were currently pursuing their master’s degrees.

Employment Status: Majority of the LPTs, 7 (70%) were employed full-time, while 3 (30%) were working as freelancers.

Nature of Work/Job Title: The majority of LPT cases, 4 (40%) were employed as administrative support staff in construction and engineering firms. The remaining participants held various roles: 1 (10%) as church administrative support, 1 (10%) as a freelance administrative assistant, 1 (10%) as a freelance social media manager, 1 (10%) as an operations expert in a healthcare company, 1 (10%) as a food and beverage server, and 1 (10%) as a municipal youth development officer.

Sector Employment Type: A large majority of the LPTs, 9 out of 10 (90%), were employed in the private sector, while only 1 (10%) was working in the public sector.

Monthly Salary: 6 out of 10 of the LPTs (60%) earned a monthly salary ranging from ₱15,000 to ₱30,000, while 4 (40%) received between ₱31,000 and ₱60,000.

B. Personality Type of the Participants

Among the ten (10) participants, five (5) MBTI personality types were identified—ISTJ, ESTJ, ISTP, ISFJ, and ESFP. The majority of LPT cases, 4 out of 10 (40%), exhibited the Introverted, Sensing, Thinking, and Judging (ISTJ) personality type, while 3 (30%) participants were identified as having the Extraverted, Sensing, Thinking, and Judging (ESTJ) type. The remaining individuals displayed a range of personality types: 1 (10%) was Introverted, Sensing, Feeling, and Judging (ISFJ); 1 (10%) was Introverted, Sensing, Thinking, and Perceiving (ISTP); and 1 (10%) was Extraverted, Sensing, Feeling, and Perceiving (ESFP).

C. Motivational Factors of the Participants

Majority of the LPTs 10 (100%) shared similar experiences with the DepEd recruitment process, describing it as lengthy and highlighting the presence of the 'backer system.' Additionally, all 10 (100%) participants emphasized salary, and personal fulfilment as key factors; 9 (90%) highlighted work-life balance; 7 (70%) mentioned workload and work environment; 6 (60%) expressed a preference for work from home. Meanwhile, 5 (50%) cited a stress-free setting, and 4 (40%) recognized the importance of opportunities for career development.

D. Implication of Findings

By analysing and interpreting the data from this study, it becomes clear that there is a need to develop tailored career pathing programs for freshmen teacher education students in colleges and universities who are reconsidering their future career plans. Given the increasing number of career shifts among LPTs, it is important to implement career and personality assessments for all incoming teacher education students at the beginning and end of the semesters within their first academic year. The objective is to create a comprehensive and responsive career pathing program managed by the Office of Student Affairs (OSA).

Although this study focused on career shifting LPTs, teacher education students may also experience career shifts in the future. Since personality types have been shown to influence one's likelihood to stay committed to the teaching profession, it is recommended that all freshmen teacher education students take the MBTI assessment. This would allow guidance counsellors, psychologists and school administrators to better understand teacher education students' goals and help them recognize their strengths and potential based on their personality types. The OSA can then use the MBTI results to assist colleges and universities administrators in designing career pathing programs and counselling specifically for freshmen teacher education students.

Furthermore, workshops and seminars offering career pathing and counselling should be provided to freshmen teacher education students to help them evaluate their career preferences in relation to their personality types. This career pathing program should be flexible and applied as needed, based on the career trends observed among teacher education students.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS**A. Conclusion**

1. LPTs are typically single females aged 26 to 27, holding a bachelor's degree and earning between 15,000 to 30,000 pesos per month in full-time administrative roles within the private sector. This implies a higher demand for females than males in the choice of educational programs.
2. The personality types that are most commonly observed among LPTs are the ISTJ and ESTJ-both types are known for being logical, detail-focused, and responsible. However, ESTJs tend to be more outgoing and proactive, while ISTJs favour working independently and at a slower, steady pace. Although they both value structure, logic, and efficiency, their social behaviours and work methods differ. These personality types are thought to play a role in LPTs' decisions to shift away from teaching careers.
3. DepEd recruitment process, competitive salary, and work-life balance as extrinsic motivation; and personal fulfilment as intrinsic motivation are the most commonly identified factors by the LPTs leading to shift their career to non-teaching roles.
4. Career pathing programs like personality and career assessment conducted by guidance counsellors and psychologists can support college and university administrators in crafting policies that prepare teacher education students for the demands of their future professions.

B. Recommendations

1. a. Taking into account their civil status, age, and monthly salary, these LPTs are well-suited to pursue further academic advancement. Engaging in graduate studies or obtaining professional certifications in fields such as educational management or instructional design can boost job satisfaction, support career growth, and empower them to create a meaningful impact beyond traditional teaching roles.
1. b. College and university administrations should actively support teacher education students by providing accessible programs and services. Ensuring that the OSA functions properly is critical for offering prompt guidance and counseling. Early support can begin with workshops and seminars held at the start of the first academic year and continue through its end to address emerging challenges. As part of the admissions or qualifying process, students should take MBTI tests to determine their motivation and suitability for the program. These results can inform semester-end workshops tailored to personality types and career assessment outcomes, fostering students' development as future educators. The DepEd may also organize career orientation sessions on the DepEd recruitment guidelines for graduating teacher education students. These are often integrated into a broader Career Guidance Program to help teacher education students make informed academic and career decisions, reducing the likelihood of shifting career paths.

2. a. LPTs with the ISTJ and ESTJ personality types frequently take on administrative responsibilities' roles. These personality types thrive in circumstances that require meticulous preparation, strict adherence to deadlines, and well-organized processes. ISTJ-type LPTs excel in roles such as policy interpreters or documentation specialists, whereas ESTJ-type LPTs thrive as program coordinators or in other leadership and management positions. LPTs should first analyze their transferable skills utilizing instruments such as the MBTI. This allows them to recognize the abilities they developed while teaching that are transferable to future positions. Once these skills are identified, LPTs can work to improve their technical, academic, and business writing abilities, focusing on activities such as report and policy writing, as well as curriculum or module development. With these abilities and insights, ISTJ and ESTJ LPTs are well-suited for non-teaching positions in government or public service, such as DepEd Division Offices, CHED, or Local Government Units (LGUs).

2. b. Incoming freshmen teacher education students are encouraged to undergo MBTI testing to enhance self-awareness and provide school administrators with insights into their personality types. Students identified as ISTJ and ESTJ can then receive targeted career pathing and counseling tailored to their specific needs and interests.

3. Considering the key motivational factors that influenced LPTs to leave teaching—such as extrinsic and intrinsic motivations—the following recommendations are offered:

a. Although LPTs may feel discouraged by the DepEd's lengthy and selective recruitment process, they are encouraged to stay updated on reforms and keep their licenses and certificates active to preserve future opportunities in the public education sector. Meanwhile, pursuing workshops, certifications, or further studies promotes continuous growth. Developing administrative skills through leadership and project management training can also prepare them for advanced roles like program coordinator, department head, or education consultant, which often offer greater fulfillment and compensation.

b. Competitive salary and work-life balance remain key extrinsic motivators for career shifts, while personal fulfillment serves as a main intrinsic motivator. LPTs seeking financial stability, flexible schedules, and meaningful work should reflect on their values and pursue roles that align with their goals. Non-teaching careers—such as curriculum design, childcare support, publishing, educational technology, community outreach, or other non-teaching positions—offer better conditions while utilizing their teaching background.

4. Key stakeholders—such as college and university administrators, guidance counselors, psychologists, faculty, and the OSA—should be informed of this study's findings to strengthen their support for teacher education students' commitment to their programs and future careers. Through collaboration in developing and implementing comprehensive, responsive career pathing and counseling services, they can significantly impact students' career development.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abulon, E. L., Bedural, Z., David, A., Florentino, J., Orleans, A., & Rungduin, T. (n.d.). Exploring wastage in teacher preparation investments in the Philippines. *The Normal Lights*, 8(2), 9-18.
- [2] Balais, A. (2020). "Stairways to heaven, but few are chosen" a psychological wellness of heavily indebted individuals (Thesis Dissertation, Pinma Araullo University, Cabanatuan City).
- [3] Bardemorilla, N., & Panlaqui, C. (2023). Pondering the phenomenon of choosing non-teaching jobs among teacher education graduates. *Ioer International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 5(2), 98-103.
- [4] Glass, B. K. (2022). The relationship between pre-service teachers' social emotional competence and teacher burnout, secondary traumatic stress, and compassion satisfaction (Thesis Dissertation, Florida Atlantic University, Boca Raton, FL).
- [5] Korunka, C., Kubicek, B., & Nalis, I. (2021). From shock to shift—a qualitative analysis of accounts in mid-career about changes in the career path. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 3.
- [6] Laher, J. M. (2024). Assessing the reasons and satisfaction of teacher education graduates in choosing a non-teaching career: Towards minimizing irrelevant employment through an effective school program. *Pedagogy Review: An International Journal of Educational Theories, Approaches and Strategies*, 2(1), 28-34.
- [7] Yurt, E (2022). Collective teacher self-efficacy and burnout: the mediator role of job satisfaction. *International Journal of Modern Education Studies*, 6(1), 52-64.